

Perspective

Engineering electrogenetic interfaces for mammalian cell control

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SUMMARY

Human body cells and our daily electronic devices both communicate information within their distinct worlds by regulating the flow of electrons across specified membranes. While electronic devices depend on the flow of electrons generated by conductive materials to communicate within a digital network, biological systems use ion gradients, created in analog biochemical reactions, to trigger biological data transmission throughout multicellular systems. Electrogenetics is an emerging concept in synthetic biology in which electrons generated by digital electronic devices program customized electron-responsive biological units within living cells. In this paper, we outline endeavors to design direct electrogenetic interfaces to control cell behaviors in therapeutically engineered mammalian cells. We also discuss prospects for the world of electrogenetics, focusing on how to engineer the next generation of therapeutic cells controlled by electronic devices and the internet of the body.

INTRODUCTION

Synthetic biology is a multidisciplinary scientific field that deals with the redesign of biological systems either to introduce entirely new capabilities or to improve existing natural properties.^{1–3} This is generally achieved by employing repurposed DNA, RNA, and protein units found in nature to construct human-designed synthetic-biological circuits that are incorporated into designer cells in order to influence and regulate the behavior of the cells.^{4,5}

These genetic circuits typically consist of three main components: a customized biosensor for signal detection, a processing module for biological information handling, and a synthetic production module for generating a custom output.⁶ The function of synthetic genetic circuits is dependent on a custom stimulus that activates a sensor module and ultimately produces the desired output⁷ (Figure 1). The nature of the trigger for the genetic circuit can be either physical or chemical, with chemical triggers offering a wider range of options but potentially posing issues such as poor bioavailability and cross-reactivity.^{8,9} Conversely, common traceless physical inducers such as light,^{10,11} temperature,¹² mechanical disturbances,¹³ and magnetic fields¹⁴ offer an efficient, safe, and non-invasive traceless approach that enables the wireless induction and activation of engineered cells with high spatiotemporal precision.¹⁵ A relatively new approach to physically controlling cell function is electrostimulation, which uses electron flow generated by electrical devices to program cell behaviors. Electrostimulation is a cofactor-free and traceless approach that can be operated by simple devices such as micron-scale electrodes, rechargeable batteries, or compact smart devices widely used in daily life.¹⁶

Electrogenetics utilizes an electric field to trigger an engineered genetic circuit implemented within designer cells. In order to design a safe and efficient electrogenetic interface, both the electrical and biological components need to be carefully considered to avoid unwanted side effects such as cytotoxicity and incompatibility with the human body.¹⁷ In general, electrogenetic-based design considerations can be divided into four main parts: the source of electrons (electronic devices and their hardware), the biosensor (membrane or cytosolic receptors), the bioprocessing unit (orthogonal platform or endogenous signaling pathway), and the production unit (which may offer slow or fast kinetics).

The main considerations in the case of the electrical components are compatibility, flexibility, and compactness of the devices with the human body, while those in the case of the biological components are tunability, reversibility, orthogonality, and specificity of the engineered genetic circuit and their hosting designer cells. The ultimate aim is to provide a high overall level of reliability, efficiency, and precision in the control of cell behaviors.

Although the foundation of electrogenetics can be traced back to microbial biotechnology,^{18,19} the present paper deals specifically with the emerging domain of mammalian electrogenetics, in which electric fields are utilized to remotely manipulate therapeutic gene expression and protein release in engineered mammalian cells.¹⁶ First, we introduce the most commonly employed electrogenetic circuits for mammalian cell control. We then look in more detail at the electrostimulation process, including both electrical devices and engineered biosensors as input senders and receivers, respectively. We next discuss implemented genetic

Figure 1. Electro-responsive mammalian designer cell

(A) Chemical or physical inducers. Chemical inducers, including small molecules (e.g., antibiotics), protein molecules (e.g., antigens), and disease-related biomarkers, can directly interact with designer cells. Physical stimuli, including light, temperature, magnetic field, mechanical disturbance, and electro-stimulation, can activate designer cells remotely.

(B) Genetic compartments implemented in electro-sensitive designer cells include biosensors, processing units, and production units. Electrostimulation can trigger a synthetic biology-based genetic circuit within designer cells to generate a customized biological output, such as protein secretion, gene expression, or induction of cell migration.

(C) Features of genetic circuits within engineered cells. Switchability: activation of the circuit exclusively in the presence of a stimulus. Tunability: level of response according to the inducer concentration. Reversibility: capacity to return to the basal level following the removal of an inducer. Orthogonality: an exclusive response to the specifically designed inducer with a lack of interaction or interference with other stimuli. Kinetics of response: fast (in minutes) or slow (in hours) upon stimulation.

circuits for converting electrical signals to biological outputs such as gene expression and protein secretion with desired kinetics. Lastly, we describe the current bottlenecks and propose future directions to adapt electrogenetics for clinically relevant applications from a synthetic biology perspective.

ELECTRICAL SIGNAL: SENDER AND RECEIVER TOOLS

The ability to generate electron flow from a digital electronic, human-compatible device and the capability to receive electrical signals by engineered cells are central requirements in electrogenetics. Here, we introduce the most common electronic devices and their complementary biosensor systems designed for electrogenetic studies. The material and structural design of the electron supply for electrogenetics setups can be divided into energy transfer devices, power-harvesting devices, and energy storage devices.²⁰ Regardless of function and structure, bioelectric devices should provide a biocompatible, compact, and safe platform for integration into cell and gene therapy programs.^{16,21,22} Here, we provide some examples of devices

developed to electrogenetically program mammalian cells for therapeutic applications.

One of the first energy transfer devices that was developed to electrogenetically control mammalian cells is based on conductive platinum anode and cathode electrodes.²³ In this case, platinum facilitates the production of acetaldehyde from ethanol at an acidic pH, and acetaldehyde works as an intermediate chemical signal to activate its own biosensor, the acetaldehyde-dependent transactivator (AICR). In contrast to this indirect approach, a new generation of bioelectronic interfaces is being developed to enable direct electrical conduction between electrodes and electro-sensitive mammalian designer cells.²⁴ For example, a miniaturized wireless-powered bioelectronic implant containing electrodes on either side of a semi-permeable membrane can stimulate engineered mammalian cells coated on the membrane. In this setup, an extracorporeal electric field generator provides wireless energy transmission to activate the bioelectronic implant. The electro-responsive biosensor system implemented in engineered cells is composed of an electro-sensitive L-type voltage-gated calcium channel (CaV_{1.2}) consisting of α_1 , α_2 , δ , and β subunits along with an inwardly rectifying

potassium channel ($K_{ir2.1}$) to reduce the resting membrane potential.

Unlike wireless-powered bioelectronics that depend on external sources of energy, power-harvesting devices such as piezoelectric implants and biofuel cells are self-sufficient energy suppliers and use resources within the human body for electron generation.²⁰ For example, a piezoelectric membrane was used to produce sufficient low-voltage energy inside a semi-permeable platinum-coated cell chamber equipped with a $CaV_{1.2}/K_{ir2.1}$ biosensor platform.²⁵ Further, a metabolic biofuel cell was developed to generate energy (0.7 mW cm^{-2} , 0.9 V) by converting excess glucose within the body into electrical power.²⁶ The biofuel cell is based on a copper-containing, conductively tuned 3D carbon nanotube composite and can provide sufficient energy to generate an electrical field or turn on a blue LED to activate engineered cells equipped with either melanopsin, a light-sensitive G-protein coupled-receptor (GPCR), or $CaV_{1.2}/K_{ir2.1}$ biosensors.

Energy storage devices such as batteries are another source of electron flow that can provide direct current (DC) to program mammalian cells. DC from batteries has been used to induce non-toxic levels of oxidative stress, including reactive oxygen species (ROS), within engineered cells.²⁷ Then, a synthetic NRF2 (nuclear factor erythroid-2 related factor 2)/KEAP1 (Kelch-like ECH associated protein 1) antioxidative biosensor system is used to convert electrical input into biological output.

CONVERTING ELECTRICAL SIGNALS TO BIOLOGICAL OUTPUTS

Upon electron generation by an electronic device, the electrical signal has to be converted to meaningful biological data inside the cell to produce the desired output.⁶ To do this, a biosensor system for signal detection, as described in the previous section, is linked to processing and production units in engineered cells to generate the desired biological output.²⁸ In this section, we introduce some of the synthetic biology-based processing and production units designed for electrogenetic studies in mammalian cells (Figure 2).

When biosensors, which include plasma membrane-anchored receptors (e.g., $CaV_{1.2}$) or cytosolic proteins (e.g., AlcR), receive electrical signals, they activate processing units by triggering either endogenous signaling pathways or orthogonal routes.²⁹ In general, the processing modules serve as a link to convey the strength, duration, and frequency of the input signal to the production unit in order to prepare a suitable response. Plasma membrane receptors often activate endogenous signaling pathways, triggering a rise of intracellular second messengers that leads to the activation of transcription factors or changes in cellular metabolism, both of which can be rewired to a therapeutic effect, either through artificial design in engineered cells or by leveraging naturally existing mechanisms.⁷ For example, $Electro$ HEK cells are electro-sensitive designer cells ectopically expressing a $CaV_{1.2}/K_{ir2.1}$ ion channel circuit that triggers calcium influx into the designer cells upon electrostimulation induced by the wireless-powered bioelectronic implant described earlier.²⁴ The change in calcium level induces dephosphorylation of the NFAT transcription factor, causing its translocation to the nucleus, where it triggers transcription of the target

gene in the presence of a synthetic expression unit containing NFAT-responsive elements. DC-actuated regulation technology (DART) is another example that capitalizes on the endogenous oxidative stress pathway to initiate the expression of a desired therapeutic protein, e.g., insulin, from a synthetic expression unit.²⁷ This system uses a DC battery as a source of electrons and a KEAP-NRF2 biosensor platform to control the expression of insulin in electro-responsive human cells in a time- and voltage-dependent manner. Similarly, the molecular elements involved in the nuclear factor κB (NF- κB) endogenous signaling pathway were engineered to express the desired gene in the presence of an electric field.³⁰ Here, electrostimulation releases the inhibitor protein (I κB) and enables the translocation of the NF- κB transcription factor to the nucleus, where it can regulate the transcription of genes of interest. In addition to these synthetically based circuits, electric fields have been shown to modulate the natural metabolic environment of targeted cells. For example, application of static magnetic and electric fields (sBE) induced an adaptive redox response by triggering ROS signaling in type 2 diabetic mice.³¹ This response reduced the circulating redox state, improved insulin sensitivity, and ultimately enabled sBE to rapidly ameliorate insulin resistance and glucose intolerance in these disease models.

On the other hand, orthogonal systems are designed to minimize crosstalk between activated components and endogenous signaling pathways.³² These systems often rely on protein domains derived from other kingdoms of life that are combined with the biosensor system. An example of this strategy is the *Aspergillus nidulans*-derived acetaldehyde-dependent transactivator AlcR, which binds to acetaldehyde and activates the acetaldehyde-inducible promoter P_{AIR} to express desired transgenes such as the therapeutic bone morphogenetic protein 2 (BMP-2) gene.²³ In that work, an electro-inducible acetaldehyde-responsive circuit was implanted in primary rat cardiomyocytes to dose-dependently regulate expression of BMP-2, resulting in increased contraction frequency (tachycardia) in targeted cells.

The production unit is involved in the creation of biological responses according to the processed signal and can be employed for a variety of applications, from the production of a user-defined protein to the activation of a biological function such as cell migration.⁶ In addition to the type of response, the kinetics can be managed by the production unit to meet the requirements of therapeutic agent delivery. The systems mentioned previously, $Electro$ HEK cells, DART, NF- κB , and AlcR, activate the transcription of desired genes from synthetic constructs. This process, transcription-based gene expression, is generally slow (4–8 h after stimulation) and is suitable for diseases that require prolonged treatments, such as infections or autoimmune diseases. Alternatively, there are other synthetic biology-based strategies that control the production and secretion of therapeutic proteins at the translational or post-translational level, which can provide a faster response to electrostimulation.^{4,33} This approach especially benefits diseases where therapeutic proteins need to be delivered on a timescale of minutes or a few hours (e.g., insulin in type 1 diabetes).³⁴ $Electro\beta$ cells are bioelectric-powered electro-responsive designer cells with the ability to respond rapidly to electrostimulation. $Electro\beta$ cells are engineered to express the $CaV_{1.2}/K_{ir2.1}$ channel as well as a proinsulin construct.²⁴ In the resting situation, insulin

Figure 2. Examples of electrogenetic setups

The electronic setups are shown at the top, with the corresponding electro-sensitive cells displayed below.

(A) A chamber contains platinum electrodes that mediate the production of acetaldehyde from ethanol. The generated acetaldehyde enters the engineered cells and binds to its receptor, AlcR, which then translocates to the nucleus, where the acetaldehyde-AlcR complex binds to the responsive binding site on a synthetic expression unit and initiates the expression of BMP-2.

(B) ElectroHEK cells. A custom-designed electrical chamber, equipped with a holder for engineered cells and an integrated electric switchboard, is implanted in an animal model. This setup can be activated by an electric field generator positioned beneath the animal cage. Electrostimulation triggers the opening of ion channels on the cell surface, which leads to calcium flow into the cytoplasm. Elevated levels of calcium result in dephosphorylation of NFAT, followed by translocation of this transcription factor to the nucleus, where it binds to the designed binding site on a synthetic expression unit and initiates the expression of insulin.

(C) Battery-generated electric fields induce electrical excitation-like oxidative stress, e.g., ROS, within engineered cells implanted in animal models. ROSs trigger the dissociation of KEAP from Nrf2. Activated Nrf2 translocates to the nucleus and induces expression of the desired therapeutic gene.

(D) An electric field generated by an electroporation device is used to rewire genetic elements involved in the NF-κB pathway to drive gene expression. Electrostimulation abrogates the inhibitory effect of I_κB and induces translocation of the NF-κB complex to the nucleus, followed by transcription of the desired gene.

is produced and stored as proinsulin within granular vesicles bound to the plasma membrane in the engineered cells. Metabolic biofuel²⁶ and piezoelectric²⁵ systems described in the previous section can be integrated with *Electroβ* to provide insulin release within just 10 min in response to electrostimulation-triggered calcium influx. Alternatively, programmable protease-mediated post-translational switch-equipped cells (so-called POSH cells) rely on orthogonal units composed of a split prote-

ase fused to calmodulin and a calmodulin-binding peptide (CBP) biosensor platform to control the release of a desired protein accumulated in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER).³⁵ Electrostimulation initiates calcium influx into the cytoplasm of POSH cells, and this triggers the binding of the calcium-responsive elements (calmodulin and CBP), resulting in the complementation and activation of the protease. Then, the activated protease cleaves the ER retention signal from the accumulated protein (e.g.,

Figure 3. Electro-mammalian cells featuring a rapid response

Electrogenetically engineered cells (e.g., POSH cells and Electro β -cells), *in vitro* setups including electronic designs and engineered cells, and *in vivo*-implanted electronic chamber devices housing designer cells in animal models.

(A) POSH cell. The implemented genetic circuit in a POSH cell contains three elements: CaV1.2/Kir2 ion channels, a split tobacco etch virus (TEV) protease fused to calmodulin and the calmodulin-binding domain (CBP), and a transgene expression cassette with an engineered therapeutic protein fused to an ER retention signal. Electrostimulation stimulates the opening of voltage-gated ion channels, resulting in calcium influx into the cytoplasm. High calcium concentrations in the cytoplasm induce the binding of calmodulin to its CBP partner, which results in the complementation of TEVp. The activated TEVp protease cuts a designed cleavage site on the therapeutic protein trapped in the ER. Removal of the retention signal allows the therapeutic protein to travel from the ER to the Golgi apparatus from whence it is secreted to the outside of the cell within about 2 h after cell stimulation.

(B) Electro β -cell. This cell ectopically expresses CaV1.2/Kir2 as well as a proinsulin cassette, which is expressed in an unstimulated condition, resulting in accumulation of proinsulin in granule vesicles. Electrostimulation opens ion channel circuits, thereby triggering a high calcium concentration in the cytoplasm, which eventually leads to membrane depolarization, followed by the release of mature insulin within about 10 min after induction.

insulin) and enables trafficking and secretion of insulin within 2 h after electrostimulation (Figure 3).

CURRENT CHALLENGES AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Bridging electronics and synthetic biology, electrogenetics relies on a wirelessly delivered cofactor-free electric field to program designer cell behavior and provides an opportunity to revolutionize future human therapies by combining minimal cytotoxicity with high efficiency and safety.³⁶

Despite the promise of electrogenetic technology for therapeutic applications, several challenges remain that must be addressed to enable successful translation into real-world clinical

settings. These limitations include limited longevity of devices in humans, potential immunogenicity and limited biocompatibility of the implanted materials, cellular exhaustion upon repeated stimulation, and power source requirements.

The longest duration of operation for electrogenetic devices in animal models so far has been several weeks.^{24,27} However, extending this duration (preferably up to several years) to meet the requirements of most human diseases remains a significant challenge, necessitating further research to develop more robust materials and engineering solutions capable of maintaining stable performance over extended periods. Another major limitation in the immediate translation of electrogenetic technology for human use is the potential immunogenicity of implanted devices.³⁷ Foreign materials can induce inflammatory responses within the

body that lead to the degradation or dysfunction of the device over time. Additionally, immune responses may impair the electrogenetic functionality of cells interacting with the device. Advances in biocompatible materials and immunomodulatory strategies could help mitigate these challenges.^{38,39} Engineered cells exposed to repeated electric current stimulation may also undergo stress or exhaustion, reducing their therapeutic efficacy over time. This issue is particularly important in systems that depend on continuous or high-frequency stimulation. To address this challenge, developing protocols for intermittent stimulation, optimizing current intensities, and engineering more resilient cells could prove beneficial. Furthermore, generating and maintaining electric fields or currents to control therapeutic devices *in vivo* require reliable power sources.⁴⁰ Current battery technologies are often unsuitable for long-term use due to size constraints, limited energy capacity, and the need for frequent recharging or replacement. Promising solutions include wireless energy transfer and energy-harvesting technologies.⁴¹ Additionally, power sources that can be recharged through physiological activities, such as body movement, represent innovative approaches to sustaining electrogenetic systems within the body.^{42,43}

To meet this aim, both the electrical and biological parts need to be designed side by side and the cooperation of electric engineers, material scientists, cell biologists, and physicians is crucial. Ideal electronic devices for electric field generation should be self-powered, compact, flexible, and compatible with human daily use.²⁰ As regards the biological component, sensitivity and specificity of the biosensor, as well as orthogonality of the process and appropriate response kinetics, are important criteria that need to be considered independently based on the disease requirements.^{4,6} Also, all engineered cells and electrical materials require a green light on safety and efficiency before translation to clinical applications. Factors to be considered include an optimal stimulation field to target the desired number of cells, improved transplantation methods, and precise integration of genetic circuits in safe harbor regions within the host chromosome. Currently, electrogenetic studies are restricted to small animal models, such as mice, where small numbers of implanted cells can have therapeutic effects. For use in humans, the number of cells for transplantation would have to be adjusted as necessary, and thus the bioelectric cell-harbor chamber may need to be scaled up. So far, bioelectric cell implants have mostly been transplanted subcutaneously in animal models (e.g., Krawczyk et al.²⁴ and Huang et al.²⁷), which may influence the efficacy of the implanted cells. Alternatively, engineering a wireless-controlled bioelectric setup and responsive cells that can be transplanted in deeper tissue than skin might enable better integration of electrogenetic setups into the physiological environment, taking account of parameters such as temperature and supply of nutrients. For example, a vibrating ingestible bioelectronic stimulator pill has been developed to stimulate mechanoreceptors in the stomach by inducing serotonin release, resulting in diminished food intake and subsequently reduced weight gain in mice.⁴⁴ Further, the combination of electrogenetics with other traceless technologies such as optogenetics or thermogenetics might lead to novel systems where a biological unit (instead of a digital device) serves as an electron flow generator. For instance, a bacterial proton pump that medi-

ates proton flow across a bacterial membrane protein complex in response to light can be used as an opto-electrogenetic tool to generate electrons for an electrogenetic setup.⁴⁵ More recently, it was shown that certain viruses can generate electrical pulses when exposed to heat.⁴⁶ This process, called pyroelectricity, could provide energy to activate electro-responsive designer cells in the future, opening up a new field of thermo-electrogenetics. Wearable smart devices such as smartphones and smart watches have also been used to control optogenetically engineered therapeutic cells transplanted within the human body.^{11,47,48} Such wearable electronic devices are often already equipped with health-related biosensors that can monitor health-related parameters.⁴⁹ These smart devices can also communicate with other ingestible or implantable devices to transfer biological data through the internet of things and even enable data analysis in real time by a physician or by a patient, which would help with self-management of disease.⁵⁰ Indeed, integration of such smart devices with next-generation electrogenetic devices is expected to revolutionize real-time diagnostic-driven therapies in the near future.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, M.M. and M.F.; investigation, M.M.; writing – original draft, M.M.; writing – review and editing, M.M. and M.F.; funding acquisition, M.F.; supervision, M.F.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

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